
ROLE OF NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS IN REHABILITATING AND EMPOWERING DESTI- TUTE WOMEN IN MYSURU

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ABSTRACT:

This study postulate the importance of NGO'S in destitute women life in Mysuru and the way they opt to rehabilitate and empower them.

Every human being has a right to live a life of dignity and peace. The basic amenities of all human-beings include food, shelter and clothes. Absence of any of these three elements leads to a life of misery and vulnerability.

The word Destitution brings the notion of inability to meet basic needs .A destitute woman is defined here as a female without adequate means of support.'Destitute 'in relation to a woman means any female who has no independent source of livelihood or is not being looked after by any family members or relative.

Mysuru is the third largest city in the state of Karnataka. Mysuru can be considered as home for destitutes. Nalvadi krishnaraja Wodeyar established home for destitute widows later on inorder to educate them Maharani's college was formed.

He also Encouraged re-marriage of widow and destitute women.

This city has many Non-Government Organizations that run at no profit. These NGOs work towards the survival and betterment of Destitute women. These NGOs are supported by many corporate groups and individuals. Even in Mysore, the public contribution to NGOs is getting higher. They incessantly work towards destitute women rehabilitation and empowerment.

KEYWORDS:

Destitute women, NGO, Empowerment, Government, Mysuru.

The basic amenities of all human-beings include food, shelter and clothes. Absence of any of these three elements leads to a life of misery and vulnerability. An individual needs an environment which ensures them the above mentioned elements otherwise it adversely affects one's physical, social and psychological state. A destitute woman is defined here as a female without adequate means of support. 'Destitute' in relation to a woman means any female who has no independent source of livelihood or is not being looked after by any family members or relative.

In terms of destitute women, these aspects have added negative impact on them because they do not have any access to any kind of services in the society.

Destitution of women is found to be due to several social disadvantages that either reflect pre-existing ones or consequence of serious problems with cognition affect and behaviour in our society. Pre-existing disadvantages include poor education, living conditions and family relationships, specifically oppression, violence, sexual abuse, subordination and devaluation inherent in patriarchal oppression. Other social disadvantages may be seen as a consequence of the problems themselves poverty, homelessness, stigmatization, exclusion from many aspects of 'normal life' and disrupted family and social networks all of which make destitute women marginalized and render them powerless.

Women in our country constitute approximately half of the entire population. Women are given the position of goddess in this country but the problems faced by them are completely contradicting their position. Women in India are in a position where peaceful social life is still a pipe dream. Gender discrimination, workplace harassment, dowry-related harassment, women-destitution are few such problems faced by women in India. Though we hear India is a democratic country and all are equal before law, destitute women are heart core reality which is closed and hidden

When women become destitute, she faces exploitation and subjected to stigma, where nobody is there to stand for her and she

left alone in the street. The destitute women are in such a state due to absence of a home, hunger she becomes forced to disregard her identity and dignity. Women are already considering as a vulnerable group in addition to that when they become destitute it doubles their sufferings in the society Women are in trouble, problem saturated thinking revolves around her and she won't be able to see her strengths and positives, due to the social confinements and limitations.

Indian culture emphasises respecting women, as a form of Devi. We all talk of gender equality, woman empowerment and female education; but how far has it been achieved in reality? In many ways, the lot of women is very less changed in reality. Though the Indian woman is well educated, today, she still faces a lot of challenges and problems, whether she dwells in rural areas or urban.

Empowerment of destitute women is the desperate need for the hour. NGOs and state home for women plays a vital role towards destitute women empowerment by providing basic education, vocational training, training for self-employment, legal aid, protection of women and self-awareness programmes, thus they strive for uplifting and mainstreaming destitute women, which in turn helps her to stand on her own and face the world.

Area of study:

Mysuru city is always known for generosity and hospitality can also be considered as Home for destitutes. During the period of Nalvadi Krishna raja Wadiyar he established Home for Destitute widows later on in order to educate them Maharani's school was formed. He also encouraged Re-marriage of widow and Destitute women.

During covid-19 lockdown of Mysuru city MCC (Mysore city corporation) has setup Rehabilitation centre for destitute at Nanjarajabahadur choutry, which gave new lease of life for some of its inmates, besides providing food and shelter to homeless destitute engaged them in vocational training-making paper covers.

According to MCC the number of women destitute in city are rising day by day. Hence it has planned to setup an exclusive shelter home for such women.

In a recent rapid survey conducted by Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana National Urban Livelihood Mission [DAY-NULM] in the year 2019, as many as 286 destitutes were identified and rehabilitated. In the Dec 29 2022 survey 202 destitutes were identified in various parts of the Mysuru city, out of which 159 were men and 43 were women.

Two prominent NGO'S of Mysuru Shaktidhama and odanadi plays a prominent role in Rehabilitating and empowering destitute women through accomidation and help destitute women in need ir-respective of their caste,creed and religion.

Strategies of Empowerment:

Shaktidhama support women who are rendered homeless by domestic violence,sexually exploited, rape victims,unwed mothers and women who are victims of human trafficking.

It provides Literacy and skill development training like tailoring,cooking bakery products, employment in honey processing unit and women managed canteens for destitute women to gain self-re-laince.

Odanadi seva samasthe is a social non-governmental organization based in Mysuru which has been working for the rescue ,rehabilitation,reintegration and empowerment of destitute and sexually exploited women .their vocational trainings include beautician course, taxi driving

The trust conducts several activities oriented towards shoring up its residents moral infrastructure including cultural capsules, meditation,recreation ,group activities and training.

The activities of odanadi have been recognised by state and central governments.Other state governments (Maharashtra, Delhi,West Bengal) have been sending rescued girls to odanadi to facilitate their rehabilitation.

NGOS becomes a home for the homeless who protects the women and girls from vulnerability. It provides trainings for the inmates to enrich their capabilities. The present research contributes for the promotion of such NGOs from the part of Social Welfare Department, so that definitely helps the destitute women and thereby reduces the stigma on them. The present research conveys the need of such institutions in the society. The institution makes them a part of the society and thereby they become free from the social exclusion.

NGOs are playing a vital role even if sometimes the government forgets. If they are given a proper back up then they can initiate many activities and improve the life status of the inmates . Lack of funding may trigger the working of it. So policies promoting the initiativeness of NGOS should be addressed for the betterment of unheard groups of women.

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